

BLACK LIGHTONIUM MATTERS

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2021

Abstract

This paper proposes a new theoretical understanding of what light or Lightonium is, what gravity causing dark matter is and, more critically, a new cognitive paradigm to tackle the imminent global warming apocalypse. Applying my lifelong and often irritating genetic autism 'superpower' of relentless pattern-play to the quantum problem of gravity, I have identified that photon light is actually a monstrous substance of matter from pre-baryonic times, that our dark night is a falling shower of heavy particle shaped liquid phase photon raindrops of light and that we possess not one but two distinct visible spectra of light, the daytime white spectrum and the nighttime microwave black spectrum. In attempting to answer for myself what really causes gravity, my conclusion that liquid light exists is based on the simple observation that in the sky, water rides light constantly like a taxi both up and down. My research has unexpectedly led me to fresh ideas concerning the unexplored noble hydrides of helium and neonium, their remarkable thermodynamic properties and a more precise location of where they might be found in deep space. Additionally, it has provided an exciting new proposal concerning the makeup of the seething solar plasma photosphere. The omission by humanity in general – and science in particular – of the very identity and existence of cold liquid phase black light is one of the proposed root causes of our current global warming catastrophe; namely, our imbalanced and disastrous obsession with hot energy and gas phase white light. By identifying the cold electromechanical properties of Lightonium, I am hoping to contribute to a necessary reversal. With apologies for my divergence to Newton, Einstein and Irving Langmuir. Blame it all on the Tourette's!

Keywords

Gravity, Lightonium, superliquid, supergas, plasma, raindrops, nucleation

Introduction

My basic hypothesis is that in nature there are not one but two visible spectra of light each with photons of different wavelength, energy, frequency, temperature, charge, velocity, mass, color, polarity, shape and – crucially – phase. I have reached the conclusion that what we perceive and refer to as 'light' is in fact the specific hot thermodynamic properties of a monstrous supersubstance of matter that has until now continued to blind both humanity and The Science. White light is the supergas phase of this supersubstance and quite simply, what causes gravity is the undefined, unknown and unexplored superliquid phase of light itself. The overlooked existence and ubiquitous presence of liquid phase Lightonium explains many unresolved phenomena from gravity to the nightly depolarization action potential across our retinas in our eyeballs while we sleep to why the social ills of racism and patriarchy still exist.

In this conjectural hypothesis, I shall introduce my method of reasoning which I call 'Autism Science' to explain what might cause gravity, what the confusing cosmological dark sector might be and what the missing quantum gauge boson of gravity might be.

Being autistic all my life, my 'autism superpower' is in the domain of recognizing and playing with obvious and obscure patterns I can observe in nature which my autistically wired brain has been doing ever since I can remember and then using the patterns to construct vast

castles in the sky. I have learned that the observed patterns do not in themselves lie and I must follow them wherever they may lead as long as the journey conforms to basic common sense and logic. The first and only rule of Autism Science is the Spock Rule of Divergence which states that one must boldly go wherever the patterns lead.

For the record, the author of this paper is not a scientist but a chef. The thought process is all my own. The very notion of the existence of black liquid Lightonium which forms the basis of this paper is entirely original. To fill in the blanks, I have turned to the Google and Wikipedia and other free open sources on the internet. Gravity should, in theory, be no more difficult to understand than any other physical phenomenon so why, then, have we effectively painted ourselves into the corner of quantum cognitive dissonance?

I will first describe my hypothesis and then test it as far and widely as I am capable of doing.

What pushes us down into bed every single night?

My ruminations begin with a simple question which I believe Newton would have approved of but sadly not Einstein. Newton made the logical assumption that two bodies in space move together because of an existing cosmic attracting force between them not unlike a macro example of Coulomb's Law or magnetism itself. His pursuit of understanding was logical. If we could travel back in time to point out the errors of his ways, he would reply with only one answer. "In that case, there must be an invisible cosmic force *pushing* them together!"

The soccer game simply does not start until someone actually applies their boot to the ball! To me, simple logic dictates that there must be an invisible pushing force in existence whose identity has eluded us to this day and the only remaining question to figure out is what exactly is doing the heavy cosmic pushing we refer to as gravity?

Gravity causes things to move along a very specific line; namely, the radius geodesic of the atmosphere connecting the outermost circumference to the innermost core. The force increases with depth which means that whatever is moving in is increasing in strength as it goes. What moves in from every point on the outer exosphere towards the core?

In our thoughts on gravity, we start with the duality of light which has been institutionalized as 'uncertain' for the last century. The photoelectric effect pointed out that light exists as both a wave and a particle. More than a century after Einstein's seminal paper of 1905 to which he was awarded a Nobel, where do we stand? The theory of relativity and the uncertainty principle combined have ensured that a century later we have made no significant advances whatsoever! On the internet we read that "light is both a wave and a particle. Probably." This is not acceptable.

Einstein again. "It seems as though we must use sometimes the one theory and sometimes the other while at times, we may use either. We are filled with a new kind of difficulty with two contradictory pictures of reality. Separately neither fully explains the phenomenon of light but together they do."

This is inexplicably still the case in 2021!

There are at least three objective observable examples of the wave/particle duality in the sky above us which together provide enough information to crack this relative uncertainty

problem wide open. Starlight, peregrine falcons and water all exhibit the same duality quite openly without any fuss whatsoever. Ohne jegliche Aufregung. There is also another place much closer to home in our own bodies to see the wave/particle duality of light to which I shall return later.

White starlight leaves our sun and moves through the solar system as uniform expanding waves of light but starlight enters the solar system, the night sky and our eyeballs as uniform contracting pinprick particles of light. Why does starlight behave in this way? The distance this light must travel to reach us from far away explains nothing about its behavior.

Olbers' Paradox, which can be traced back to Kepler in 1610, remains essentially unresolved to this day. Why, indeed, is the night sky visibly black? Do the terms 'invisible, dark and black' all mean the same thing?

Is the behavior of starlight similar to refraction where light enters a denser medium changing both velocity and direction? At the very least, we can observe that white light travels as expanding waves when moving against gravity and as contracting particles when moving with gravity. The behavior of starlight is our first indication that the wave/particle duality of light is intrinsically linked to the passage of day and night. We may also enquire whether nighttime darkness is itself a contracting dense medium?

We start with the empirical fact that light possesses the mysterious duality. In starlight, we can observe light acting like either a wave or a particle. Waves of starlight move against gravity and particles of starlight move in line with gravity. Ergo, the duality of light is intrinsically linked to gravity. This conclusion based on observable patterns in the sky is crucial.

We continue with the observable patterns.

The fastest animal on the planet is the peregrine falcon who routinely reaches close to 400 km/h in pursuit of fresh starling sushi for lunch. These raptors display a similar duality in their flight patterns. By being a perfect outstretched wave function, the bird can catch the rising thermals to heights over a kilometer up before changing shape into a contracted tucked-in particle and dive bombing to unprecedented speed.

We know that electrons and protons exhibit the duality so why not massive birds in flight? By itself, the birds can tell us nothing about the duality of light but since it plainly shows the same wave/particle duality operating in the same directions as starlight, we may include the birds in our scientific reasoning who reinforce the notion that waves travel against and particles move together with gravity. We can also observe that the particle function is a heavier falling version of the wave function. Energetic expanding waves defy gravity and closed contracted particles take advantage of gravity. The question now is whether light possesses both a non-heavy rising wave version and a heavy falling particle version? Does the very duality of light illuminate the missing quantum boson of gravity?

The real clincher is the way water behaves in the sky similar to light. After starlight and peregrine falcons we arrive at water, our favorite hydride on earth. The dielectric constant of a solvent is a measure of its polarity and water is very polar. The study of dielectric properties concerns storage and dissipation of both electric and magnetic energy in materials. When an

external electromagnetic field is applied at infrared frequencies or less, the molecules are bent and stretched by the field and the molecular dipole moment changes. Paramagnetism explains how some materials are attracted by an externally applied magnetic field and form internal, induced magnetic fields in the direction of the applied magnetic field which allow electric charge to flow between them.

We know that water possesses its remarkable shape-shifting abilities due to the hydrogen bonds within the molecules. We know that polar covalent molecules align their dipole moments accordingly in the presence of a polarized electromagnetic field. We know that energy is required to convert a liquid to vapor and conversely, water must lose energy to condense from vapor to its cold heavy liquid phase.

The simple point is that when light passes over or through water, electrons flow from one to the other in one of two possible directions depending only where the electrons are located. We are investigating how water changes to both gas and liquid phases and how these transitions are mediated by the transfer of photons and electrons.

The crucial piece of objective and empirical evidence in the unification of gravity is the way water behaves above us in the sky. In rising clouds we *sometimes* observe a strong rippled wave pattern and in raindrops we *always* observe particle shapes. I believe that a correct understanding of this phenomenon opens the door to a proper understanding of what causes gravity. We cannot escape the conclusion that water displays an identical duality of matter as observed in light.

The wave pattern in clouds is most noticeable when the clouds are stretched out and wispy thin often rippling in a structured wave pattern across the entire sky. By themselves, we cannot determine a fixed wave pattern in clouds. However, since we do observe a fixed particle shape in raindrops and since clouds and raindrops travel in the same direction as both starlight and falcons, we can conclude that a *sometimes wave pattern in clouds* is good enough to establish the wave/particle duality in the behavior of water in the sky.

These wavy clouds are wrongly referred to as Kelvin-Heimholz clouds who explained that this 'instability' is created by the wind. I must raise my objection that the wind is far too random to create such exquisitely formed wave ripples in clouds and that we must look deeper than the wind for an explanation. We need to start at the very point of phase transition nucleation at the first point of evaporation and raindrop formation.

Everywhere in the universe is a raindrop formation universality from sulfuric acid rain to water to iron and plasma raindrops. The Science is still not clear about what drives this process.

The Science explains that raindrops form when water vapor condenses on tiny particles of dust floating in the atmosphere. Although correct about the drops coalescing around a sticky universal particle, it is neither dust nor smoke nor microplastic. Rain attenuation or rain fade is the phenomenon of rain absorbing microwave radiation at frequencies above 10 GHz.

How about a positively charged microwave photon particle behind the formation of raindrops?

Primary or first order nucleation is the first step in a new thermodynamic phase which occurs at both cloud and raindrop formation and involves the formation of both gas and liquid molecular bubbles. When liberated from the liquid phase, water molecules form into round vapor bubbles and when shoved back into liquid phase, clouds form round droplets of water. The cohesive surface tension of liquid water results in closed round bubbles whether full of gas or of water. Secondary or second order nucleation occurs when the micro liquid bubbles coalesce together in the formation of one macro superbubble at a unique location whether out there in deep space or wrapped around the hot solid core of the earth as the homogenous oceans. Secondary ocean superbubble formation is the end of the phase. From here, they either slosh round and round or heat up and rise up into the gas phase as steam.

If water exhibits the same duality as light, it follows that light is causing water to act this way. If water demonstrates that the wave function is gas phase behavior and the particle function is liquid phase behavior, it follows that in the sky above us light too exists in both a gas and liquid phase.

In this paper, I propose the existence of liquid phase light which has inexplicably escaped scientific attention to this very day! Indeed, our entire universe is entirely full of slow-moving liquid light and that that this hitherto unknown substance is to blame for both gravity and the dark cosmological sector. The historical Aether does in fact exist and it consists entirely of liquid photons of light!

The next fact to consider is the time of day that rain usually falls.

Water is moving constantly up and down our skies but down on earth, initial raindrop seeding occurs chiefly during the dark hours of night. Google confirms that rain usually starts falling from 3am until light. Alternatively, rain often starts during the late afternoon or early evening at the same time as most lightning strikes. There is no doubt that a strong connection on earth exists between initial raindrop seeding and the darkness of night.

Considering our observations, we may conclude that:

1. Waves of light move against gravity and particles of light move with gravity.
2. Particles are the heavy falling versions of lighter rising waves be they light, water or hungry birds.
3. Water exhibits both gas and liquid phases in the sky and they are both formed on the back of light.
4. Raindrops are usually seeded at night which points directly to a falling heavy liquid phase photon of light which also happens to be black as the night itself.

And so, we arrive at the monstrous but inescapable conclusion that just as daytime is the flow of fast rising hot gas phase white photon waves of light so is nighttime the flow of slow falling cold liquid phase black photon particles of light and that daytime is the rising negatively charged polarized high frequency electromagnetic field of hot white light and nighttime is the falling positively charged low frequency electromagnetic field of cold black light.

In this paper, the darkness of night is no longer considered the mere absence of light but, more correctly, the presence of black spectrum liquid phase Lightonium. The white light of day is a negatively charged electromagnetic field and the black light of night is a positively

charged electromagnetic field. Light must be correctly identified as a 'substance of matter' with physical properties that are still largely unknown and unidentified. Science can no longer avoid this fact.

It is this substance that moves inexorably from the edge of space into star cores bumping baryonic matter along the way into heavier phases of matter. It is even logical that a real liquid substance is responsible for gravity by turning gas baryons into heavier liquid baryons.

It is true that the black night sky makes an unlikely and counter-intuitive candidate for a vast cosmic superliquid that leaves black holes in its wake and kicks Jupiter back and forth like a ping-pong ball bobbing in the bath tub yet it also borders on the incomprehensible that the very idea of nighttime black liquid light seems never to have been proposed at all.

What kind of liquid possesses a density lower than the lightest of gases?

The visible black spectrum of Lightonium

If nighttime is the passage of black light as daytime is the passage of white light there must be not one but two visible spectra of light in existence, a white spectrum and a black spectrum.

I am most proud of this discovery. Not only does light exist around us in two distinct phases – ground state cold liquid phase and hot gas phase – they are both visible to us. That this is not obvious defies an easy explanation.

Put quite simply, The Science and all the great polymaths of light have overlooked the very existence of the black spectrum liquid phase of light! As an 'error of science' this must rank with considering the earth the very center of the universe.

In answer to Herr Olbers, the night sky is visibly black not merely from an absence of white light but rather from the presence of visible black light!

Using Autism Science, we have managed painlessly and successfully to bypass the centuries old impasse and without any expensive useless machinery arrive at the shocking but inevitable conclusion that the missing unifying quantum gauge boson of gravity and the cosmological dark sector particle is none other than the black liquid photon raindrop which has been hiding in plain darkness all along!

What more could one wish for as the errant quantum boson of gravity than a heavy, falling photon with both mass and momentum?

At this point, a brief discussion about the nature of light is unavoidable. Light is not merely an oscillating electric and magnetic field and thermal radiation with a wavelength visible to the human eye but something much more: a vast pre-baryonic substance of matter.

Lightonium is just a regular substance of matter with mind bending properties

If light does indeed exist in both a gas and liquid phase, this can only mean that 'light' is a substance of matter with regular properties of matter like mass and phase transition. If the liquid phase of light has mass, then the gas white phase of light must also possess mass as unfathomable, unfashionable and unmeasurable it may be. If the photon is capable of

changing phase and shape from a bubble to a contracted drop like the water molecule, the photon must also be the equivalent of a 'composite molecule of Lightonium' and is not a fundamental particle at all although smaller than the quarks in the hydrogen atom. The sheer vastness of the quantity of 'light' indicates that it is not a baryonic substance at all but a much older pre-baryonic substance of matter possessing truly monstrous and unimaginable both hot and cold thermodynamic/electromechanical properties. In fact, our young little baryonic universe could not even begin to create a substance with such exotic properties. Lightonium might as well be a time travelling alien visiting us from the distant future. A liquid with a density of about 0,0001% of the density of air might well be considered an alien!

When it comes to energy absorption, storage and dissipation, photons act remarkably similar to water on a more cosmic dimension. Photons act like polar covalent molecules with permanent dipole moments with an ability to handle infinite numbers of electrons. Water clouds can reach lengths of several kilometres and absorb impressive amounts of energy as demonstrated by lightning bolts. Lightonium, on the other hand, appears capable of stretching to lengths of trillions of km and transporting both heat and momentum over these distances. It is difficult to even imagine let alone comprehend the full electromechanical properties of this alien substance of matter.

For most of recorded human history, our forebears worshipped the stuff as a living deity which it might still be after all. The very name we have given this substance – Licht – is itself problematic, misleading and confusing. Named after its specific gas phase, the liquid phase of Lightonium is not light at all but both heavy and dark. As a substance, Lightonium is a better name for it.

We are looking at a supersubstance of matter which exists in our universe as a supersolid, a superliquid and a supergas.

A perfect and real blackbody? The real Bose-Einstein condensate? A real quantum spin liquid moving around stars and planets?

Googling 'supergas', I found myself looking at sneakers. There is an ideal gas but no notion of a supergas.

Lightonium in its respective supergas and superliquid phases is a cosmic supertransporter of both heat and momentum – and probably mass as well – conserving them both over staggering untold distances.

What manner of liquid substance needs to be cast into stellar furnaces to be boiled into its hot gas phase? We are used to boiling water in a pot and watching the bubbles rise and leave as steam vapor but a pot as big as our sun heated to 15 million degrees belching out hot steam waves of bubbles to distances of hundreds of billions of km away? Come on!

Superparamagnetism is a form of magnetism which appears in metallic nano-particles associated with iron, cobalt, nickel and some alloys. Lightonium must also possess such extreme magnetic properties on the Angstrom scale. Its 'intermolecular forces' are stronger than gluons and the strong nuclear force.

The entire visible universe is comprised of Lightonium – a cosmic bosonic supersubstance of matter – in three distinct phase states: a supersolid ground state matrix, round evenly spaced superbubbles of superliquid galaxies and in their core, phase transition to supergas we otherwise refer to as white light.

The magic happens in the liquid nexus phase in a giant cosmic conspiracy between Lightonium and baryons. We measure the passing of time as the process of baryons turning from fresh energetic gas phase into a heavy old solid phase of being. Lightonium, on the other hand, moves from solid to gas phase in front of our very eyes. What this implies about time itself is unknown.

Atmospheres and lightning

Atmospheres conduct electricity all the way from the outer cold exosphere to the inner hot rotating liquid core. Gravity is an electromagnetic phenomenon mediated by photons and electrons which carry both heat and momentum. Many forms of lightning discharge exist from superbolts of visible lightning on Jupiter to UV electrical discharge from the glowing wall of hydrogen at the far edge of the solar system. The various discharges can produce a wide range of electromagnetic radiation depending on the speed of the electrons.

The Science has an incomplete understanding of stellar and planetary exospheres. Difficult to study for obvious reasons, they display the most exciting electrochemical and thermodynamic activity. It is here to look for the peripatetic noble hydrides.

The Science also openly admits that lightning is poorly understood which is a shame as lightning is one of the most empirical objective phenomena of all that point directly to the ignored existence of black liquid Lightonium.

Lightning most often strikes in the late afternoon or early evening. Is this not compelling enough?

Upper atmospheric or ionospheric lightning occurs well above normal storm clouds and are referred to as transient luminous events. They have been observed in far-ultraviolet images of Jupiter's upper atmosphere high above the altitude of lightning producing water clouds.

The movement of electrical charge between the surface of the earth and the ionosphere is called the global atmospheric electrical circuit which has a daily light phase followed by a dark phase at night. During the day the air gets charged and at night it discharges. Polar covalent molecules spend their time moving up and down in constant flux between gas and liquid phases. The ionosphere glows constantly from its upper invisible UV range to its lower visible range.

Our atmosphere is a giant electrical circuit board composed of different charge conducting molecules, water being the chief culprit. Most gas and density layers in the atmosphere besides the greenhouse gases consist of substances moving up and down carrying charge this way or that in constant daily flux between their gas and liquid phases. Each density bubble layer has a different liquid covering the base. The lowest rung, the troposphere up to about 12 km, is dominated by water and is covered by a superbubble of liquid water everywhere.

When it comes to explaining lightning, The Science seems remarkably lost at sea. The Google reports thus:

“Lighter, positively charged particles form at the top of the cloud. Heavier, negatively charged particles sink to the bottom of the cloud. When the positive and negative charges grow large enough, a giant spark - lightning - occurs between the two charges within the cloud.”

Googling the following questions, I was met with ignorant silence. Does lightning contribute to gravity? Does lightning heat the earth core? Nothing really there in the theory about this.

A much better, deeper and satisfying explanation for what induces lightning is the falling low frequency emf of the nightly shower of black liquid Lightonium as it comes to play in the late afternoon or early evening as the sunlight fades.

Light has the biggest effect on polar covalent molecules with permanent dipole moments. Water is the first example which by adopting the shape and behavior of light can absorb tremendous energy, enough on earth to zap off 10 million bolts a day. An average bolt possesses 300 million volts at a temp of about 30,000 K so we are talking of a daily influx of 3 trillion volts of electricity shot with force directly into the earth!

There are many types and colors of electrical atmospheric discharges both visible and not like red sprites, blue jets, green ghosts and ELVESs, ‘Emission of Light and Very low frequency perturbations due to Electromagnetic pulse Sources’. And then there is dark lightning created in the icy near freezing darkness by molecules with the weakest intermolecular forces of them all, London dispersion forces.

Chasing errant polar covalent all over the universe is an autiste joy. From water and ammonia to molten magnetite iron ore in the earth’s core all pointing their little magnetic dipoles in the same direction to others like fluorine halide, carbon monoxide and nitrous oxide, there is one polar covalent compound missing from our gaze. It does not exist here on earth and only in the last few years have the guys in Germany proved that it even exists somewhere out there at all. We are talking of primordial helonium or the helium hydride ion. This stuff is potentially super exciting with unexplored energy storage and dissipation potential that might be to blame for powering gravity everywhere in the universe.

In fact, lightning understood correctly explains the very cosmic mechanism of what powers the unstoppable power and might of gravity in building galaxies and the entire baryonic universe. It demonstrates how the First Law of Thermodynamics is fundamental in describing how stars work and how gravity is the cold work phase of light itself. Lightning demonstrates how energy from white light loops backwards through water and other polar covalent molecules like magnetite and helonium in a closed conserved system. It goes even further and demonstrates how life on earth was created by the interplay of hot white light and cold black light using polar covalent baryonic compounds as cosmic tantric sex toys.

Rods, pupils and REM

As mentioned earlier, there is another place much closer to home to witness the wave/particle duality of light and that place is In your bathroom mirror and your very own eyeball.

The next major challenge to the existence of nightly black light is in our brains. The optic nerve grows directly out of the brain to observe, read and see visible light and as our brains are aware of white light so must they be aware of black light should it exist.

As strange as it sounds, our subconscious brains must know all about black light while simultaneously our conscious brains know absolutely nothing at all! Separated in time by only a few waking moments, a chasm of deep cognitive dissonance between them spans the length of the entire universe!

Looking it our eyes, there are two channels to absorb light, the white expansive iris with cones and the black contracting pupil with rods.

Right there in the center of our eyeballs we can see the two different eye antennas designed to see both white and black light! The iris is very wave shaped and the pupil correspondingly particle shaped. The duality of light exists within our eyeballs.

The retinal depolarization action potential at night involving the rods and umami glutamates is a case study in quantum electrodynamics of photon mediated interactions among charged particles and a demonstration of how the quantum boson of gravity operates at the quantum scale.

Rods are responsible for night vision and have no role in color vision. Rods are longer than cones which might correspond to the longer microwave photon. At night, rods depolarize and release the neurotransmitter glutamate. This results in a loss of negative charge and a gain of positive charge. In other words, at night while we sleep something induces away electrons across our retinal membrane.

Another phenomenon which science struggles to explain is REM in our sleep and the paradox of why our brains are as active at night as in the day while our bodies are in the state of deepest unconscious paralysis.

Jung had no explanation why light causes both humans and dogs to sneeze or why people everywhere dream consistently of falling. Here, again, we may point our little fingers directly at the black liquid photon monster.

The subconscious brain 'sees' the black photon raindrops falling through our retinas and 'reports back' in our dreams as if we ourselves are doing the falling. Talk of cognitive dissonance!

Getting too little sleep at night is associated with low bone mineral density and higher levels of osteoporosis. While we sleep, our bone and muscle and brain densities increase as if entering a denser or liquid phase state of being. During the day we switch to a vertical position with our brains on top adopting a lighter brain density state.

Many anomalies of sleep can be explained by the falling shower at night of black Lightonium raindrops through our bodies and brains. It would also adequately explain the so-called light and dark cycle. The night is as active as the day.

Cosmic Microwave Background – the real evidence

After the failure to identify the fairly obvious existence of black liquid Lightonium, the accepted scientific Nobel awarded explanation for the mysterious existence of cold expanded photons everywhere in the universe must surely rank amongst the greatest of all science blunders and requires immediate rectification.

We are surrounded everywhere by cold mobile microwave photons of light. Scientists were initially bewildered by the fact that the CMB can also be measured at night but this seems to have been swept under the carpet.

I would place the existing theory of the CMB together with relativity and uncertainty as the main reasons why quantum mechanics has painted itself into a corner.

Did these cold expanded microwave photons originate as hot plasma which mooched around and cooled over the last 13,4 billion years or are these cold expanded photons in the ground state of liquid Lightonium on the way to gas phase transition?

What will it take, Your Honor, to reopen the case and have the verdict overturned? What will it take to accept the CMB as 'objective and empirical evidence' of the existence of black liquid light?

(A hypothetical question in parenthesis. If microwave photons indeed possessed a visible spectrum, what color range would it fall in? Black is the answer. A coincidence?)

Were these microwave photons ever carbon dated? The only thing that the CMB really proves is the existence everywhere in the universe of cold microwave photons of light. It tells us nothing about where they come from or at what temperature or color or shape they started out or anything about the so-called Big Bang origin theory of the universe.

I do not know what it would take to revise the existing scientific explanation of the CMB to provide the main empirical objective evidence of the very existence of black liquid Lightonium. I believe it must be done and I am proposing this very thing in this paper.

Superliquids make superbubbles

To answer 'what is gravity?' one must answer two separate questions. Firstly, what exactly is doing the heavy cosmic pushing through space and time and secondly, what exactly is powering this universal push? We have identified the positively charged black spectrum electromagnetic field of liquid Lightonium as the guilty party behind the heavy pushing and now we shall attempt to identify what lurks behind this unstoppable cosmic flow of black liquid light.

The mechanism is actually well described by the fundamental First Law of Thermodynamics which explains unknowingly perhaps what gravity is. Within star systems, we find hot work energy converted into cold work energy in a closed conserved loop – hot electricity out and cold electricity in.

We must start with the two stages of gas-to-liquid phase nucleation. Nucleation is how first order phase transitions start and is the beginning of a new thermodynamic phase. Cohesion and surface tension exist which results in primary bubble or round droplet nucleation depending on the phase. The primary stage of gas-to-liquid phase transition involves the

formation of round liquid droplets and the secondary stage involves the formation of its constituent gigantic ocean superbubble at its specific gravity and density location with vapor clouds, rain and lightning. Strong hydrogen bonded hydrides are the heaviest liquids and weak Van der Waal bonded noble hydrides are the lightest.

Homogenous nucleation occurs away from the surface of an immersed fluid and in this case, we are talking about the first molecular gas nucleating into cold liquid helium bubbles while immersed in the depths of the primeval cosmic molasses, the fabled aether, the immense expanding ocean of cold black liquid Lightonium.

Once again, we start with water. Water, ammonia and HF. although volatile to evaporate at low temperatures, are all molecular hydrides held together as liquids through the strong dipole-dipole hydrogen bonds and have high boiling points. We are familiar with these compounds especially water.

Noble gas hydrides exist largely in theory only. Helonium, neonium and argonium have largely avoided astrophysical detection and remain poorly understood. Their weak molecular bonding, their large dipole moments and their cold temperature in isolation all allude to remarkable electrochemical properties; so much so that speculation is rife that they birthed stars, planets and even moons.

The existence of helium hydride was only confirmed for the first time in 2019 just in time for Covid. Scientists from Germany's Max Planck Institute for Radioastronomy discovered the molecule's signature in our very own Milky Way galaxy using NASA's airborne SOFIA observatory but as good as this is, primordial helium hydride remains undetected.

Left alone unto itself, the first baryonic molecule to form – the helium hydride ion – is a stable molecule and the strongest known acid in the universe but we still don't have a clue where it is. The Science thinks that all primordial helium hydride gas molecules disappeared down the throat of molecular hydrogen but the truth might be different. What if the first molecular baryon gas progressed on to its liquid phase, nucleated into liquid helium hydride droplets and still exist today as the liquid ocean skin surrounding all galaxies and stars? There is even some possible evidence for this.

In August 2018, NASA cited results by ALICE on New Horizons to confirm the existence of a glowing ultraviolet hydrogen wall at the outer edges of the solar system as detected in 1992 by both the two Voyagers.

This double wall of hydrogen can only be a bubble surrounding the entire solar system and as a bubble of hydrogen must be a bubble of liquid hydride. Is this our primordial helium hydride generating UV flashes of energy out there in the deep space black cold nothingness?

The Nucleate Pool Boiling Experiment on the International Space Station demonstrated that in conditions of zero or micro gravity, bubbles behave differently than on earth. In space, bubbles or drops that form cannot rise or fall and instead coalesce into one large bubble right where they are.

The essential question that needs asking is this: under conditions of zero gravity, what proportions can a primordial superbubble of helium hydride attain? Could we find one with a

diameter of, say, three quintillion km? The Science seems to feel that zero gravity exists absolutely nowhere in the universe since gravity is still defined incorrectly as the force that attracts any two bodies together but once again, I must diverge. The implications of the existence of black liquid Lighonium is that gravity exists only within the electrodynamic superbubbles of galaxies and is not caused by body mass but by heavy liquid electrons tossed by baryons onto other baryons powered initially by white light and induced in the night by black light.

This habit of liquids to form closed round shapes, whether as full liquid drops or gas enclosed bubbles, is not at all restricted to those with strong hydrogen bonds as even ozone does it. Electrostatically speaking, however, the two most significant groups are heavy liquid hydrides with strong hydrogen bonds and non-heavy liquid hydrides with weak London forces; namely, water, ammonia, hydrogen fluoride, helium, neon and argon.

It appears that all rotating cosmic bodies with atmospheres are surrounded by gigantic liquid superbubbles dominated by the true baryonic supermolecules still in place since primeval days of yore. In a fractal sense, galaxies are no different from the carbonated bubbles floating in your favorite fizzy drink. Bubbles as well as substances operate under a strict fractal pattern regime starting with galaxies and ending with moons. Each successive superbubble is wholly contained within the larger superbubble atmosphere like Russian babushka dolls. Balanced in place by their outer layers of lifting gases and their inner cores of heavy solids, all they can do is bob about.

I am proposing that each galaxy and star is surrounded by a gigantic bubble ocean of liquid helium hydride over which is an atmosphere of helium hydride clouds dripping flakes of acid rain and constantly discharging short slow bursts of dark X-ray or ultraviolet lightning into the positively charged electromagnetic river of black liquid photons cascading down the rabbit hole beginning their long, non-stop journey into their cores for a hot bath and fitting of new golden fairy wings.

Helium and neon appear to make ideal energy storage super-batteries and through their own little weather systems out there in the darkness, are possibly capable of generating sufficient energy to power the entire gravity system beneath be it a galaxy, star, planet or moon. Essentially, these different noble superhydrides account for the sizes and composition of their celestial bodies and explain why the gravity fields on stars, planets and stars are all of different strengths.

Although neon is the fifth most abundant element in the universe, it is rare in the atmosphere of planets which is why I propose that as galaxies and stars are encased within superbubbles of helium so are planets enclosed within superbubbles of neon and argon in turns all lunar precincts from our own fluffy little moon to Tian hanging around Saturn.

Our upper atmosphere radiates strongly in the infrared. Airglow or nightglow which originates from self-illuminated gases is the faint luminescence of earth's upper atmosphere and is not noticeable during the daytime.

The Cosmic Infrared Background is the possible measurement of the continuous infrared lightning generated by neon rain in the earth exosphere. In the day, huge invisible clouds

of neonium must form at the very edge of space to be converted into powerful invisible infrared lightning discharges when the earth rotates into darkness. I can only speculate that these nighttime infrared surges of radiation into the atmosphere are what is captured by the CIB measurements.

Although abundant on earth as molecular argon, it is only on the moon where argon hydride seems to be active. LADEE's Neutral Mass Spectrometer determined that the moon's atmosphere is composed mainly of helium, neon and argon. Their relative abundance is dependent on the time of day on the moon. Helium peaks at 1 am, neon at 4 am and argon at sunrise. As demonstrated in Vegas, the noble gases glow. Neon emits a red glow, helium pale yellow and argon glows blue. Depending where the moon is, it glows from reddish to yellow to bright white.

Argon produced directly by stellar nucleosynthesis is dominated by the alpha-process nuclide argon-36, better known as argon hydride or argonium. Solar argon contains 84.6% argonium which contrasts with the inexplicably low abundance of the stuff in earth's atmosphere comparable with that of neon on earth. Argonium was only detected for the first time in space in 2013 which was the first time a noble molecule was ever detected.

Acids are molecular compounds that release hydrogen ions. The noble gas hydrides are all nasty acids. As picked up from the Apollo missions, lunar dust or regolith causes a wide range of problems from breathing issues to adhering to everything from spacesuits, windows, solar panels and radiators, degrading seals and whatever else it contacts. The stuff is abrasive and microscopic and finds its way into everything.

These ideas about helonium, neonium and argonium are highly speculative. I only mention them to explain gigantic electrical superbubbles within superbubbles.

Earth-bound gravity fields

As attempted to describe above, gravity is caused by the cold liquid phase of light itself. What the Lord giveth with one hand, He taketh with the other. Light or Lightonium is apparently a staggeringly vast primordial substance of matter in which our entire baryon universe is floating almost as an after-thought.

Lightonium is so exotic and mysterious to us mere mortals that we are either completely blinded and bamboozled by it or we wish to worship it as a living deity with hymns and animal sacrifices. Compared to more familiar baryon substances, Lightonium possesses much lower density yet much higher supermagnetic and other internal superforces and electromechanical properties. In truth, science has only just scratched its surface. We are talking of a cosmic supersubstance and a supertransporter of both heat and momentum. We are too highly aware of its bright gas phase and too little aware of its black liquid phase which is directly to blame for la gravité und die Schwerkraft.

Lightonium melts into liquid droplets upon entering galaxies until they are entirely filled with liquid streams of Lightonium heading directly to the black hole at the core. Upon entering star systems, they are imbued with additional energy and momentum from the outer ocean superbubbles converging at the bottleneck near the solar core. As an incompressible quantum spin liquid, the black particles of night are incompressible. In order to get through the

contracting bottleneck towards the solar core, they must increase their speed, energy and frequency while dramatically shortening their wavelengths. Planets play a large role in this.

Here on earth, gravity is caused by the falling shower of night. As the planet rotates over a 24 hour period, half of the planet is constantly in the dark. We experience directly both an indirect and direct gravity field.

The former which we encounter as constant atmospheric pressure weighing down on our heads is explained by Pascal's Principle which states that "pressure in a fluid is transmitted undiminished. A change in pressure applied to an enclosed fluid is transmitted undiminished to all portions of the container and the fluid. The total pressure in a fluid is the sum of all pressures from different sources."

This is the force of gravity that literally keeps us pinned to the ground at all times. The entire combined weight of the atmosphere above one's head is communicated downwards through air pressure and spread evenly over the entire surface.

There is a second gravity force-field that comes down on us directly at night with the shower of black photon rain which literally slams us down into bed and pushes through our brains mashing our eyeballs as they go and completing the light/dark cycle of melatonin production and gives us weird dreams of falling and death and stuff. It is no surprise that both melatonin and melanin are polar covalent compounds and both activated by light.

The moon has a slower day of a full month. This gentler rotation velocity is still enough to maintain an active albeit weaker atmosphere.

The moon and our tides

Descartes was the first philosopher who suggested that the ocean tides are caused by the moon and in 1687 Newton explained that tides result from the gravitational attraction of the sun and moon on the oceans of the earth. Descartes believed that the moon acted on the waters of the ocean by downward pressure whereas Newton demonstrated that it acted upon the oceans by forces of attraction not unlike Coulomb forces or even magnetism.

According to Autism Science, Newton was wrong and Descartes was correct because there are no possible pulling forces of attraction between the moon and the oceans. Additionally, the atmosphere of the moon is fully contained within the lunar superbubble and does not extend anywhere near to the earth surface and hence, any and all lunar gravity fields are far removed from the earth. How, then, does the moon affect the ocean tides on the earth below?

The only possible solution is that as the moon moves slowly around the earth, it exerts a displacement pressure down through the heavier layers of the earth atmosphere onto the nearest earth surface thereby squeezing the oceans. Thus, in effect, the moon does not directly cause high tides but the *low tides*.

The tidal patterns on the surface of the earth are caused by the gravity field of the earth pushing the weight of the moon down. If it appears as if high tides are formed directly under the moon, this is only the result of angular momentum of the flow of gravity and the rotation of both celestial bodies.

Dark matter rain falls into the photosphere before changing phase directly into white light

The simple question is this. If 'light' is a substance of matter which exists around us in both a gas and liquid phase and if the liquid phase of light is responsible for gravity, does liquid light also undergo primary and secondary nucleation in its solid-to-liquid transition?

A star no more creates nor destroys light any more than my stove made the soup cooking in the pot. If stellar cores do not create photons during the process of nucleosynthesis, where in stars are they to be found? If dark matter as black liquid Lightonium merely passes through stars in its transition to the hot gas phase, where in stars does all the magic take place?

It's called Jean's Instability and Hydrostatic Equilibrium all rolled into one. What comes out must first go in. Relative to us primates, what goes up must first come down. That's what they mean when they sing that the night is closing in. Where do all those vampire and Lilith myths come from anyway? Lilith means 'night' in the closest Hebrew word. They are not wrong to assign the black night a female gender.

The universe is composed of fractal patterns. Light and water are similar in behavior and different only in scale. Water is a galactic supersubstance and Lightonium is a cosmic supersubstance. If water falls as rain and collects on the surface of planets as a gigantic ocean superbubble, does Lightonium also fall as rain onto the surface of stars into a gigantic ocean superbubble? Apparently so!

In this paper, I wish to propose the radical idea that the solar photosphere is actually a seething ocean on the surface of stars formed by falling raindrops of liquid Lightonium and consisting of bubbling liquid Lightonium boiling away and ejecting vast plumes of steaming Lightonium gas a.k.a. white light or more precisely, our very own cosmic supergas.

According to this theory, photons are not produced in the core and merely rain down into the ocean photosphere furnace before boiling up and away again as photon steam.

Solar photospheric granulation? Nothing more nor less than phase transition liquid-to-gas primary superbubble nucleation.

Unfortunately, besides my predilection for chasing the universal fractal patterns, I can offer no further proof for this radical new idea. The similarity between the surface ocean on planets and the surface ocean on stars might, however, explain the vast temperature anomaly between the photosphere and atmospheric corona of the sun. Just as a pot of boiling water cannot exceed the boiling point of the liquid within so too the temperature of the photosphere cannot exceed the boiling point of liquid Lightonium swirling about of around 6000 K despite the vastly hotter gamma radiation emanating from the core and pulsating through it.

The density of the photosphere is estimated at about 0,0001% the density of air at sea level which would make hot liquid light about 14 times less dense than hydrogen deuterium gas. Of course, cold liquid light would be denser than the photosphere but still less dense than hydrogen gas. This is a crucial property of gravity causing black liquid Lightonium

If the photosphere is a boiling pot of liquid Lightonium with a boiling point of around 6000 K, this would hint at the existence of superparamagnetic intermolecular forces far stronger than

hydrogen bonds by a wide margin. These unknown and thus unexplored 'intermolecular liquid photonic forces' would be needed to explain how the much less dense photon liquid can dominate much heavier liquids like water. In effect, while expanding white light bubble waves form a lighter gas than hydrogen, contracting black light raindrops form a heavier liquid than water or mercury. Lightonium supergas transports more heat and Lightonium superliquid transports more momentum than baryons of any ilk could even dream of.

Liquid Lightonium is what holds galaxies together and possesses real collective weight and form gravity causing Dark Matter everywhere. Between galaxies, Lightonium consists of the supersolid entangled solid phase of Lightonium. We can deduce this because light from galaxies neither expands nor contracts and seems to travel in straight lines besides normal phenomenon of light diffracting through different media.

Tracing our cosmic supersubstance Lightonium from its supersolid 'superfluid entangled matrix' ground state at 0K, we may identify four separate and distinct states of Lightonium matter. They correspond directly to so-called dark energy, dark matter, plasma and white light.

1. Between galaxies, we find the cold Lightonium supersolid matrix at 0 K. This is Dark Energy in the way it behaves and is in the visible black spectrum.
2. Within giant expanding superbubble cavities, solid phase Lightonium melts and nucleates into first order cold liquid phase Lightonium superliquid raindrops which drip and flow constantly from the outer circumference towards the central core. A.k.a. the Cosmic Microwave Background or nighttime, this is Dark Matter at 2,725 K and is also in the visible black spectrum. This is what causes gravity.
3. Wrapped around the nuclear cores of stars, we find the second order nucleation of liquid Lightonium in the hot liquid phase photosphere plasma superliquid ocean at around 6000 K. Although also in liquid phase, since it is now in the visible white spectrum and makes up 99,9% of all visible matter in the universe and behaves very differently, we may consider the superliquid Lightonium plasma as a state of matter in its own right.
4. Lastly, we find the hot gas phase of supergas Lightonium vaporizing off the bubbling boiling plasma on the surface of stars a.k.a. white light or daytime in a range of hot visible spectrum temperatures.

We have lastly identified the solar plasma as hot liquid Lightonium. Other types of plasma are solar wind, nebulae and lightning. The first two emanate directly from the bubbling solar plasma. Lightning is made up of liquid phase particle shaped electron plasma. Whatever exotic supercharged type of substance electros really are, they also switch in the presence of Lightonium between gas and liquid phase.

Hydrogen atoms are cosmic mustard seeds

A final Gedankenexperiment on Luftmensch Airlines.

There are two ways to break up plastics. One is to burn them and the other is to spread them in stinking piles all over the earth and let them slowly decay and decompose into ever smaller

pieces of micro plastic. As small as they get, they never seem to lose their innate 'plasticness'. They are now in all fresh water systems and in most animal guts.

Now imagine the natural death of a universe like ours. The heat has all gone out. Everything has fallen back and collapsed into a big entropic heap of acids, heavy metals, poisonous isotopes, nuclear decay, all the elements in one big heavy heap, slowly decaying and grinding away until the bits of fairy dust are all smaller than our quarks. Do they lose their substance of matter properties? No, they do not! They all gradually turn into one pile of decayed cold compost, crushed into one entangled mess, ready to start the process of growth all over again waiting for someone or something to throw in a pile of fresh energetic hydrogen mustard seeds to grow into huge galaxy trees dripping once again with shining ripe star fruit.

Viewed as a substance of matter a hundred billion years old with the same properties of matter scaled up to another dimension, light and its active 'composite molecule', the photon, indicate the very existence of other universes and that our young baryonic universe is just another one 'on the pile'.

In this way, Lightonium could be a substance made from exotic heavy metals with insane magnetic and electrical properties yet of insanely small bits of matter as well.

We find a pile or a rotating sphere of solid phase cold inert photons at 0 K. Giant superbubbles of liquid helium hydride grow with amazing energy storage abilities. The unique properties of energized electromagnetic superbubbles create massive cold momentum vectors and thrust them collectively towards the core. Deep within the supersolid yet superfluid matrix of solid phase Lightonium, round cavities appear which begin melting the substance into nucleated drops of liquid Lightonium. These rain drops of liquid Lightonium move with both purpose and direction towards the core carrying along everything in its path, stealing energy away from them and bumping them into heavier liquid and solid phases while they cascade collectively into the stellar superpots for boiling into vapor.

Possible explanations behind the failure to identify liquid Lightonium

Is it logical or self-evident that since daytime marks the passage of white light in one direction, nighttime marks the passage of black light in the other? Is it logical or self-evident that since white light transports both heat and momentum over apparently infinite distance, it is an unfathomable substance of matter from a different dimension entirely?

Many ideas in science have touched on the existence of black liquid light such as the ether, Newtonian fluids and gases and more recently the Bose Einstein Condensate only to be forcibly yanked away. Patriarchy is to blame for the simple reason that black liquid Lightonium is one half of the duality of life and the primordial archetypal matriarchal energy force field in nature. This dark mysterious intangible force field was actively removed from religion with the advent of modern monotheism and actively blocked from systems of power and even knowledge. There are many examples of this. The later colonial philosophies of race reinforced this harder and deeper.

If liquid Lightonium exists, formal scientific identification and acceptance of it will result in immediate, fundamental and long-lasting improvements in the ongoing social inequalities of both racism and sexism as well as unifying quantum gravity.

Final observation

Gravity moves directly into the sun. Hot gases rise up together with white light and cold liquids fall down together with gravity. Ergo, gravity is caused by the cold superliquid version of sunshine.

Conclusions

As collective humanity, we still have a fundamental misunderstanding of what light is which has led us directly to global climate catastrophe which needs revising and reversing immediately. This 'light' stuff is simply a regular substance of matter from a different dimension altogether. Gravity is merely a result of the cold thermodynamic conserved kinetic energy momentum properties of liquid phase black spectrum light applied over trillions of km and just like us peeps, light comes in both black and white packages. Night is black light outasight alright, aait!

In the Duality of Light chart, we may add the following. Under 'wave': cosmic supergas phase, daytime, visible white spectrum, bubbles & male and under 'particle': cosmic superliquid phase, nighttime, visible black spectrum, round drops & female.

So, what causes gravity? Nothing but the passing river of black liquid Lightonium which leaves polar covalent gas molecules in its wake as heavier polar covalent liquid molecules.

Is this theory testable?

Very simple. Design and build an instrument to test the given parameters of black liquid light. Obviously, white light cannot be used in this sensor at all. A way must be found to theoretically test for black spectrum cold microwave low frequency heavy photon particles. Reconsider the Cosmic Microwave Background in a fresh light and make a deliberate attempt to connect it directly with nighttime.

See the light and see the darkness too. At this point in human history, spiritual endarkenment must take precedence over spiritual enlightenment.

I propose that the easiest place to look for and find the black liquid photon of Lightonium is in raindrops. Throw enough money and particle physicists at raindrops and eventually the falling heavy liquid phase particle of light must emerge from the darkness and show her face.

In the quantum theory, there needs to be a solid theoretical underpinning and mathematical definition of the very existence of a visibly black positively charged electromagnetic spin-2 photon quantum gauge boson of gravity carrying both mass and momentum. I can only suggest it.

List of revelations and revisions

1. Gravity is also an electromagnetic interaction mediated by photons and electrons.
2. Night is visible black liquid light which puts Olbers' Paradox to rest once and for all.
3. White light is a negatively charged electromagnetic field of photon supergas and black light is a positively charged black body radiation electromagnetic field of photon superliquid.

4. Light is a much older pre-baryonic substance of matter with monstrous physical and thermodynamic properties as if a time traveller from the distant future. A photon is a composite set of fairy-dust Lightonium particles and can more accurately be described as a 'molecule of Lightonium' although smaller than quarks. Its 'bits of matter' are smaller and denser, its internal binding energies are stronger and its hot and cold electromechanical properties are larger than anything we have ever yet conceptualized. Our understanding of what light is needs to be thoroughly revised especially now due to imminent and catastrophic global warming.
5. In stars, dark matter transitions from cold liquid phase to hot visible gas phase or white light.
6. There are 2 visible spectra of light, a white spectrum and a black spectrum. 'Black' is not the 'absence of light' but the 'presence of black light.' Both are visible as we have two distinct channels of light through our optic nerve into our brain. The pupil and rods are meant to see low energy black light.
7. The Cosmic Microwave Background is the real evidence that we are surrounded everywhere by cold moving microwave liquid Lightonium. In nature, light moves from a black cold liquid to a hot white gas and not the other way around as described by the current scientific theory attached to the CMB.
8. The existence of the nightly earthly flow of black liquid Lightonium with its low frequency emf explains other mysterious phenomena like gravity, lightning, the light and dark phase in nature, raindrop seeding universality, REM in our sleep and 'dreams of falling' and lastly, natural death.
9. Lightning is induced by black liquid Lightonium when it appears in the late afternoon.
10. The entire hidden cosmological sector of both dark energy and dark matter is a result of black Lightonium in a supersolid phase outside of galaxies and a superliquid phase within.
11. Our entire baryonic universe is immersed in an expanding sea of black liquid Lightonium.
12. The moon's gravity does not directly create high tides on earth but low tides through the atmospheric pressure it exerts directly above the earth by virtue of the earth's gravity field.
13. Plasma as found on the photosphere surface of the sun is a liquid and thus not the fourth state of matter but rather the fourth state of Lightonium.
14. The existence of black liquid Lightonium also explains the gender duality within nature and its scientific omission explains the persistence of social racism and patriarchy.
15. We need to get our focus off the hot gas phase of light and move collectively to the cold liquid phase of light. By focussing only on the gas phase of light, we are effectively reversing and unravelling the process of life creation and are in real danger of destroying ourselves and most life on our planet. This is the most urgent aspect of my paper.
16. According to my proposed theory of the existence of black liquid Lightonium, the photon is the unifying quantum gauge boson of gravity but this time the heavy falling positively charged particle shaped liquid phase visible black spectrum spin-2 photon of light.